

Experimental and Numerical Investigation of Shape Memory Alloy Hybrid Composites with Elastomeric Interface

G. Pisaneschi^{1*}, T. M. Brugo¹, P. Cosseddu¹, G. Scalet², and A. Zucchelli¹

¹ Department of Industrial Engineering (DIN), University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

² Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture (DICAr), University of Pavia, Italy

* Corresponding author (gregorio.pisaneschi@unibo.it)

AMDUNIBO

ADVANCED MATERIALS DESIGN UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

ELETTROSPINNING LAB

COMPOSITE MATERIALS

SMART MATERIALS

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

Paolo: the student

I want to use SMA to create a mobile flap to increase the resistance force in braking

È un'idea fantastica!
Let's do it! (you do it)

Andrea: the visionary Professor

Gregorio: the SMA PhD guy

It's a bad idea,
the composite is too stiff,
the interface will break,
heating is a problem,
cooling is a problem..

Let's use an elastomeric interface, trust me, I did 1000 time, it will work

Tommaso: the experienced in composite (Also the guy who make things work)

Povolo, M., Brugo, T. M., & Zucchelli, A. (2020). Numerical and Experimental Investigation of Al./CFRP Hybrid Tubes with Rubber-like Interlayer.

I can help!

Giulia: the experienced in SMA FEM

(a) Epoxy-Config. tube.

(b) Rubber-Like-Config. tube.

THE PROOF

- 0.5 SMA wire (As 95°)
- 3.5% prestrain
- 6 Ampere

WHY IT WORKED?

STATE OF THE ART

Figure 3 Acid-cleaned nitinol actuator, magnification = Figure 5 Sandblasted nitinol actuator, magnification =

PAINE, JONES, & ROGERS, (1992)
Nitinol actuator to host composite interfacial
adhesion in adaptive hybrid composites.

Baz, Ro, (1992).
Thermo-Dynamic Characteristics
of Composite Beams

STATE OF THE ART

Yuan, Bai, Jia. (2016).
Enhancement of interfacial bonding strength of SMA smart composites by using mechanical indented method

Modifying method	Chemical etching [15]	Hand sanding [9]	Silane coupling agent [10]	Twisting method [13]
value	3%–18%	17%	91%	500%

Baitab, et al. (2020).
Tensile behavior of multilayer 3D smart woven composites embedded with SMA wires.

STATE OF THE ART

- l_c : critical embedding
- σ_{ult} : fiber tensile strength
- r : radius of the fiber
- τ_y : interfacial shear strength

Kelly and Tyson (1965)

$$l_c = \frac{\sigma_{ult} \cdot r}{\tau_y}$$

- **Embedding length \gg Critical length**
but the SMA doesn't brake

- **Mode I** is predominant:

The **necking** of the SMA wire cause **debonding**

SPOILER

- The solution to SMA integration in composites is to eliminate **Mode I**
But most of the work is to increase **interfacial shear strength**

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION

1. Manufacturing
2. Testing
3. Characterization of the materials
4. Finite element analysis

1. MANUFACTURING

Specimen with or without elastomeric interface

- 0.2 mm SMA wire (Af -25°)
- 0.22 mm GFRP prepreg
- 0.5 mm KRAIBON

- Preliminary specimen
L_embedded = [1/4" 1/2" 1"]

- Final specimen
L_embedded = 1/2"

2. TESTING - METHOD

Customised Pull-out tests of different embedded length specimen

2. TESTING - RESULTS

- + Initiation of Martensitic Phase Transformation (MPT) within the free wire
- × Completion of MPT within the free wire and initiation within the embedded
- + Initiation of debonding
- × Completion of debonding

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3. CHARACTERIZATION

SMA wire
tensile test
(dotted line)

SMA FEM
curve
(red line)

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS - MODELING

1. 3D-2D FEM validation
2. 2D ax-sym FEM
Shared Topology: starting stress value
3. 2D ax-sym FEM with CZM
DOE: Optimization of parameters

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS – SHARED TOPOLOGY

	τ average (MPa)	δt (mm)	σ average (MPa)	δn (mm)	R (-)	α (-)
EP	18	0.04	9	0.04	0.1	1
KR	5.75	0.87	3.5	0.004	0.1	1

First Attempt
 CZM
 Parameters

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS - DOE

	$\tau_{average}$ (MPa)	δ_t (mm)	G_t (MPa·mm)	$\sigma_{average}$ (MPa)	δ_n (mm)	G_n (MPa·mm)	R (-)	α (-)	
DOE 1			0.6405						
			0.63						
			0.6195						
		18.3	0.07	0.366			0.13		
		18	0.04	0.36	8	0.012	0.048	0.1	1
		17.7	0.01	0.354				0.07	
DOE 2			0.0915						
			0.09						
			0.0885						
		35.4	0.06						
		23.6	0.05				0.5		
DOE 3			0.354	8	0.012	0.048	0.1	1	
		14.16	0.03				0.01		
		11.8	0.02						
DOE 3					0.24	0.96			
				16	0.06	0.24			
		17.7	0.04	0.354	8	0.024	0.0964	0.1	1
					4	0.012	0.024		
					0.004	0.016			

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS - DOE

	(MPa)	(mm)	(MPa·mm)	(MPa)	(mm)	(MPa·mm)	R (-)	α (-)
DOE 1	7	1	3.5	7	0.01	0.035	0.1	1
							0.2	
							0.3	
							0.4	
							0.5	
							0.6	
							0.7	
							0.8	
							0.85	
DOE 2	7	1	3.5	7	0.01	0.035	0.85	1
	6		3					
	5		2.5					
	4		2					
	3		1.5					
	2		1					
			0.5					

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS - RESULTS

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS - RESULTS

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS - RESULTS

CONCLUSION

- The elastomeric interface can effectively be used to integrate SMA
- Other method all fail before or when the SMA MPT reach the matrix
- A method of optimization of CZM parameters have been tested

UPDATES

- Experiments with different embedding lengths
- Study of the effect of clamping in the SMA modelling
- Tensile traction/compression characterization of KRAIBON
- Study of the effect of the thermal effect
- Improved FEM modelling
- Improved DOE optimization method of CZM parameters
- ...

FUTURE WORKS

- Tailoring of the elastomeric interface
- Electrospinning of the elastomeric interface
- Thermo-Mechanical Characterization of SMA and KRAIBON
- Experiments/Numerical investigation with Shape Memory Effect
- Design of new SMAHC
- ...

AKNWOLEDGEMENT

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